

EFFECTIVE METHODS AND TECHNIQUES FOR DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

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Abstract. *The student's personality, emotions (emotional state), and productive-will have a direct relationship to their professional development in terms of their spiritual and moral (motivations, needs, directions of value, and reflective culture) realms (practical preparation, voluntary self-management). High levels of the student's general cultural training, his personal attributes, the availability and degree of understanding of what motivates creative activity, pedagogical experience, and intuition are necessary for the manifestation of pedagogical creativity. The efficient strategies and tactics for enhancing communication skills are reviewed and discussed in this article.*

Keywords: *effective methods, success, professional communication, educational system, ability to formulate abilities, competence, communication skills.*

ЭФФЕКТИВНЫЕ МЕТОДЫ И ПРИЕМЫ РАЗВИТИЯ КОММУНИКАТИВНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ

Аннотация. *Личность учащегося, эмоции (эмоциональное состояние) и продуктивность будут иметь прямое отношение к его профессиональному развитию в плане его духовно-нравственной (мотивации, потребности, ценностные установки, культура рефлексии) сферы (практическая подготовка, добровольная самодеятельность). управление). Для проявления педагогического творчества необходимы высокий уровень общекультурной подготовки учащегося, его личностные качества, наличие и степень понимания мотивов творческой деятельности, педагогический опыт, интуиция. В этой статье рассматриваются и обсуждаются эффективные стратегии и тактики повышения коммуникативных навыков.*

Ключевые слова: *эффективные методы, успешность, профессиональное общение, образовательная система, умение формулировать способности, компетентность, коммуникативные навыки.*

The student's overall set of personal characteristics determines how well he communicates with kids. The management of a diversely structured student community is primarily focused on the intended functions of moral and professional qualities. The student's place in the system is strengthened by his high level of development in these traits, which make him psychologically appealing, approachable, and understanding to other pupils. The student's improvement of professional competence, which is determined by the level of professional education, experience, and individual abilities, as well as by his or her desire for ongoing self-education and self-improvement, creative attitude, and responsible attitude, is a crucial component of the student's professional development.

Among people create conditions for the relationship and the student to be perceived by the students not as a leader but as a leader. In the professional sphere, the following qualities are necessary:

- general culture;
- humanitarian orientation of personality and activity;
- school problems, systematic vision of pedagogical phenomena and processes, the ability to make creative decisions;
- possession of modern pedagogical and managerial technologies, a culture of communication;
- creativity of thinking and activity in the professional sphere, the presence of a culture of reflection.

Recently, the issue of training the student in innovative activities has become relevant development of the creative potential of the individual as a result of the main condition for ensuring the student's readiness to work in changing conditions and the improvement of the quality of teaching and educational work of the modern school.

The elements of the student's professional culture are not generally understood in contemporary thought or practice. Axiological, technological, human, and creative components make up a professional instructional culture, according to many scientists. The student's capacity to build on a specific algorithm while taking into consideration educational activity, the development of his professional activity, and the stages of goal-setting, planning, organizing, evaluating, and correcting constitutes the technological component. Pedagogical technology aids in understanding the core of pedagogical culture, discloses historical changes in approaches, and explains the direction of action based on social relationships. Pedagogical culture serves as a regulator in this situation.

The ability of the student to theoretically apply the technology of the pedagogical process, perform practical activities, make a personal contribution, enrich it with new ways and methods, and continuously seek out the best answers is a manifestation of pedagogical culture. A professional student's culture is distinguished by their capacity to generate innovative, most efficient ways to deal with the situation at hand based on their own and their peers' experiences. A complex synthesis of the student's cognitive, emotional, willful, and motivational mental worlds results from their creative thinking activities.

Inventiveness and aptitude in education. First and foremost, creativity is a complete focus of the entire bodily and spiritual nature. It covers all five of a man's senses, not just sight and hearing. Additionally, it encompasses the body as well as the intellect, will, feeling, memory, and imagination. The focus of all things spiritual and material should be creativity. A non-traditional method to solving instructional difficulties is predominant at the creative level (high level of self-awareness in professional activity), where improvisation and intuition are significant factors. The learner frequently starts to develop instructional skills in various forms. The most significant goal of pedagogical action is its creative aspect.

This is due to the variety of pedagogical situations, the uncertainty of which requires changing approaches in analyzing and solving the problems arising from them. Pedagogical creativity does not arise spontaneously as a component of professional pedagogical culture, for its development, objects and sub-conditions are necessary.

Many scientists now consider the creative problem to be a "crisis of the century," and many believe that education, namely modern schools, hold the key to solving it. In this circumstance, the student's personality comes to the fore; his most important professional quality

is his capacity for invention. Similar to this, a student's pedagogical activity can address issues with secondary institution operation, meet the demand for highly skilled professionals, efficiently address societal challenges, and be adaptable to changes in the society of modern technology.

Based on the reorganization of previous experience and the development of novel combinations of information, skills, and products, creativity is an activity that produces something new that did not previously exist. There are several levels of creativity. In order to reach a higher level of creativity, a completely new approach must be developed that modifies the object's or field of knowledge's typical appearance. One level of creativity is characterized by the use of already existing knowledge and the expansion of its sphere of application. Continuously being creative is an educational activity. According to a Methodist philologist from the 19th century, it is important to highlight the "word gift" in the gathering of educational skills. Along with being reliable, fluid, and understandable, V.P. Ostrogorsky also has the capacity for speak beautifully and attractively. In special literature, usually three independent areas of the art of speech are considered: stage speech, eloquence and speech as a means of pedagogical communication. In educational work practice, such types of speech activity are most often manifested in speech.

Competence is the attribute of a person who possesses consciousness, authority, skill, knowledge that enables him to judge anything, and knowledge in all respects. It is a systematic manifestation of knowledge, skills, qualifications, and personal characteristics that enable him to successfully complete the functional tasks that constitute the core of professional activity. Competence is an integrated mental education that encompasses the information required to complete a certain set of activities as well as the capacity to set them up, plan their completion, select and implement suitable solutions, and assess the outcomes of actions. As part of a comprehensive, integrated education, competency development entails the development of the matching psychological functional system.

This means that the professional qualification of the student is a prerequisite for the formation and development of his pedagogical skills, which constitute the content of pedagogical culture. The level of proficiency in the study of a person is one of the priority indicators modern student and head of school. The main component of the professional culture of the student is the acquisition of human science compensation in the process of mastering human science technologies.

In conclusion, the problem of professional and pedagogical competence development is one of the most important problems of modern pedagogy today. Because professional skill in any profession is the sum of a person's personal characteristics, theoretical knowledge and practical skills. The level of professional skill for the student is a qualitative indicator of his development as an individual. Thanks to this compensation, the interaction of the student with the student's personality is carried out on a fundamental scientific basis, at the level of high humanitarian technologies. Pedagogical culture is a part of human culture, in which the spiritual and material values of education and upbringing, methods of creativity, educational activity, which includes the achievements of various historical periods, are necessary for the socialization of the individual.

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